

Reading Road Map for the Enrichment of Comprehension Skills of Grade 5 Pupils

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to enhance the reading comprehension skills of Grade Five pupils using Reading Road Map. The study made use of quasi-experimental research design where an adopted-enhanced Reading Road Map was the primary data-gathering instrument. One section of Grade Five Pupils, which is composed of forty-eight (48) pupils from Cabatang Elementary School contributed to the study. Percentage and weighted mean were used in the statistical analysis of data.

Meanwhile, the study revealed in the mean pretest scores before using the Reading Road Map were the reading performance of the respondents falls under average in terms of sequencing of events, inferencing and noting significant details falls on good level and identifying the main idea belongs to the fair level only. Meanwhile, there were changes in the mean post-test of the respondent's score. Despite the little improvement in the scores, the level of sequencing of events still falls under average level, inferencing and noting significant details still fall under good level. Identifying the main idea improves and falls under a good level. The little improvement in the mean score of the respondents indicates that somehow using Reading Road Map contributes to the reading comprehension skills of the respondents.

KEYWORDS: identifying the main idea, sequencing of events, noting significant details, inferencing, reading comprehension, Reading Road Map.

INTRODUCTION

One communication in human life that is very necessary to be mastered is the language. English as an international language has very wide use in every nation and because of that fact, then English become significant in student's life.

The four basic skills in the English language such as reading, listening, speaking, and writing is important to be developed by the students. Reading process is very complex. It lets the students get information and knowledge from different materials. According to the psycholinguistic point of view, reading is not mainly a visual process. It also occurs in non-visual which the information comes from the brain of the reader or what they already know about reading. Studies state that it is not enough to see sentences in front of the eyes, someone must know something of the language in which the material is written, its subject matter, and about the reading itself. In relation to reading comprehension, Ngabut (2015), mentioned four things that need to be reviewed such as cognitive reading skills, history of reading instruction, variables involved in comprehension types and purposes of reading [1]. This means that reading itself is useless without comprehension and interpretation of the meaning of the text.

Reading comprehension is important for this adds meaning to what is read. It occurs when words on a page are not just mere words but thoughts and ideas. Comprehension makes reading fun, enjoyable and informative. It is generally needed to succeed in school, work, and life. When students participate in constant reading, it improves their vocabulary and comprehension of concepts which are important for understanding and overall performance.

The most important goal in every reading program is improving reading comprehension. For that reason, the purpose of many activities in learning to read is to increase comprehension abilities. Able to gain the information to improve the knowledge of the readers is the competence of reading.

Nowadays, many pupils are having difficulties, especially in reading comprehension, particularly in the English language. With this, there is a need for effective strategies and activities that will help the readers easily comprehend what they read.

Lots of researchers noticed that students are quite weak in English in general and in reading. They still find difficulties in reading comprehension. They also rely on word-to-word translation when reading English. Al-Sobh (2021) stressed that there are two main reasons why students have poor comprehension skills. Firstly, when teaching reading, most English teachers concentrate on assessing students' comprehension at the word and sentence levels rather than concentrating on teaching reading comprehension.

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Secondly, students' lack of reading comprehension strategies is also considered a major cause of students' poor comprehension skills [2],[3].

According to Ghazo&Sobh (2021) indicates that students have a high estimation of certain problems they encounter in reading comprehension as a result of the complexity of the texts, anxiety, and word recognition (decoding)[4].

This is identical to the problem encountered by the students in Cabatang Elementary School. The reason for the researcher to study reading strategies that can help them to increase their level of reading comprehension.

Plocher (2016) revealed in his study that Reading Road Map is the easiest among the strategies he used in his study. It is enjoyable and helped the learners to complete the given task more accurately than the reading comprehension strategy they normally use [5]. Using reading road map, the pupils will be able to improve and enhance their comprehension skills. The teachers will be able to know and realize the effect of using Reading Road Map in the reading comprehension of the students. In this case, they will be able to use this strategy to improve their students' comprehension.

The reading road map strategy represents the bottom-up model, as readers start from part to whole ideas, interpret assumptions and draw inferences, or they need to find out the overall purpose of the text or to get the main ideas of the text. According to Browne (1998), the bottom-up model begins with the knowledge of letters, to sounds then words and how these words are formed to make sentences [6]. This is a part to whole model as it goes from partial to whole knowledge. This model is so effective in early childhood, especially for students as young learners. It is effective for the emphasis here is on recognition of the letters, to words.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To determine the effect of Reading Road Map as reading strategy for the enrichment of comprehension of Grade 5 pupils in English in terms of sequencing of events, inferencing, noting significant details and identifying the main idea.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research used a quasi-experimental design. This study used a pretest-posttest experimental research design. Pre-test and post-test is a quasi-experimental research design. It allows uncomplicated assessment of an intervention applied to a group of study participants. Quasi-experimental studies can use both pretest and posttest measurements as well as nonrandomly selected control groups. The design was applied to investigate the effect of applying the Reading Road Map as enrichment for comprehension skills of the Grade 5 learners in English

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were one section of Grade 5 pupils in Cabatang Elementary School for the academic year 2022-2023, which consists of forty (48) pupils. The grade five students answered the pre-reading and post-reading comprehension assessment before and after using Reading Road Map material to determine the effect of using it on students' reading comprehension skills.

Sampling Technique

The respondents were purposively selected by their expected manifestation of enhanced reading comprehension skills. The researcher selected the respondents purposively because they are capable enough in using the Reading Road Map in terms of sequencing of events, inferencing, noting significant details and identifying the main idea. The sample size of 48 pupils is based on the stated sampling technique.

Research Procedure

Before a letter of request for approval to conduct the study was handed personally by the researcher to the school principal of Cabatang Elementary School in Cabatang Tiaong, Quezon, the researcher formulated the instruments and will undergo internal validation and external validation by a school head and master teachers.

The researcher by then will be ready for the administration of the reading assessments for the target respondents. Letters duly signed by the principal of the school to conduct the study and for the administration of reading strategy were secured.

Upon the approval of the principal, the researcher was taking charge of the administration and distribution of the reading assessment to the respondents. The researcher distributed the pre-reading assessment to one section of grade five students for assessing their initial reading comprehension skills performance.

After the retrieval of the answered reading assessments, the researcher then discussed the four comprehension skills in line with the researcher's prepared lesson exemplar. Each reading comprehension skill was taught per week using Reading Road Map as a strategy and enrichment activity. After 4 weeks of teaching and answering, the researcher then distributed the post-reading assessment to assess the reading comprehension skills of the respondents after using Reading Road Map.

The accomplished pre- and post-reading assessments were sealed to ensure the confidentiality of contents.

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Research Instruments

The main instrument of the study is the Reading Road Map adapted from <https://momenvy.co/reading-road-map/> [7]. The instrument was enhanced by the researcher to be applicable for the four comprehension skills.

The reading assessments consist of pre-test and posttest, which is composed of 10 questions for each comprehension skills such as sequencing of events, inferencing, noting significant details and identifying the main idea with the total of forty (40) questions which undertake several stages of development.

Each type of reading assessment was composed of different sentences, passages, paragraphs and short stories which were adapted from different sources focusing on different reading comprehension skills.

The researcher also prepared four lessons focusing each comprehension skills. Every lesson taught a skill in reading through Reading Road Map.

The validation of the instruments was initiated by which they evaluated and validated by chosen experts in the field of research to attest the correctness and the reliability of the contents and phrasing of the items therein.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered by the researcher from the pre and post reading assessment before and after using Reading Road Map was analyzed using frequency and percent distribution.

The level of significance between the dependent variable and independent variable was analyzed using paired T-test at .05 level of difference. Means and standard deviation will also be applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Mean pretest score of the respondents before using Reading Road Map

Reading Comprehension Skills	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Sequencing of Events	4.71	2.74	Average
Inferencing	6.00	2.01	Good
Noting Significant Details	6.50	2.49	Good
Identifying the Main Idea	3.96	1.76	Fair

Legend: 8.00 – 10.00 Excellent; 6.00 – 7.99 Good; 4.00 – 5.99 Average; 2.00 – 3.99 Fair; 0 – 1.99 Poor

Table 1 presents the results of the pretest of the respondents before using the Reading Road Map. The reading performance of the respondents before the use of Reading Road Map falls under Average in terms of sequencing of events with the mean of 4.71. It means that the students have a little difficulty with this skill, thus they must be improved. Meanwhile, inferencing and noting significant details with different means of 6.00 and 6.50 falls to a good level which means that the students need to do more exercises or practice reading about the topics. However, identifying the main idea belongs to the fair level only with the mean of 3.96. It implies that the students have difficulty in identifying the main idea in the paragraph or passages given to them. Hare and Milligan (1984), Stevens et al. (2019) and Boudah (2013) stated that identifying main ideas should be given focus since it may affect the reading comprehension skills of the pupils [8]-[10].

Table 2. Mean posttest score of the respondents after using Reading Road Map

Reading Comprehension Skills	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Sequencing of Events	4.88	2.77	Average
Inferencing	6.75	2.03	Good
Noting Significant Details	7.06	2.30	Good
Identifying the Main Idea	4.65	2.11	Good

Legend: 8.00 – 10.00 Excellent; 6.00 – 7.99 Good; 4.00 – 5.99 Average; 2.00 – 3.99 Fair; 0 – 1.99 Poor

Table 2 shows the results of the posttest score of the respondents after using the Reading Road Map. Based on the results, there were changes in the mean of the respondent's score. Despite the little improvement in the scores, the level of sequencing of events still falls under average level with the mean of 4.88 which is the highest among the four skills. Whereas sequencing is one of the reading comprehension skills that contributes to students' ability to understand the text. Meanwhile, inferencing with the mean of 6.75 and noting significant details with the mean of 7.06 improves and falls under good level. Identifying the main idea also improves and falls under a good level. The little improvement in the mean score of the respondents indicates that somehow using Reading Road Map contributes to the reading comprehension skills of the respondents.

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Table 3. Difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the respondents before and after using Reading Road Map

Language Proficiency	Pre-test		Post-test		t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)
	M	SD	M	SD			
Sequencing of Events	4.71	2.74	4.88	2.77	-0.488	47	.628
Inferencing	6.00	2.01	6.75	2.03	-2.773	47	.008
Noting Significant Details	6.50	2.49	7.06	2.30	-1.762	47	.085
Identifying the Main Idea	3.96	1.76	4.65	2.11	-2.200	47	.033

Legend: If p-value Sig. (2-tailed) $\leq .05$, then it is statistically significant.

If p-value Sig.(2-tailed) $> .05$, then it is NOT statistically significant.

Table 3 presents the significant difference between the pretest and post-test after the treatment. Results show that the mean posttest score in terms of sequencing of events (4.88) is higher than the mean score in the pretest (4.71), representing a significant improvement in reading comprehension in terms of this skill. Gouldthorp, Katsipis & Mueller (2017) provide evidence that sequencing is an important skill for children's comprehension of narrative texts and has implications for reading education and intervention programs [11]. However, these data were subjected to statistical analysis which revealed that there is no significant difference ($t=0.488$; $p=.628$) between the pretest and posttest of the respondents after using Reading Road Map. Thus, the hypothesis is supported.

In terms of inferencing, the mean posttest score (6.75) is also higher than the mean pretest (6.00) of the respondents representing a significant improvement in reading comprehension skills. Elleman (2017) discovered that inference instruction was helpful for students' general comprehension [12]. Students who received inference instruction in a small group benefited more than students in a larger group. However, when tested at a .05 level of significant difference, the $t=2.773$ and p-value of .008 is statistically significant.

In terms of noting significant details, the mean posttest score (7.06) is also higher than the mean pretest score (6.50) representing an improvement after Reading Road Map. The result of the study is the same as the study of Imam, Abas-Mastura & Jamil (2013) which is disturbing to note that students even performed low in noting details [13]. While Calahan and Clark (1988) believed it to be the easiest skills [14]. Results revealed that using Reading Road Map found no significant difference ($t=1.762$; $p=.085$) in terms of noting significant details. Thus, the hypothesis is also supported.

In terms of identifying the main idea, the mean posttest score (4.65) is higher than the mean pretest score (3.96) which has the second greatest improvement among the four skills. Results revealed that the respondents found it easy in studying the topic which is identifying the main idea using the reading road map. The t-value of -2.200 and p-value of .033 reveal that there is a significant difference at .05 levels.

Solis et. al. (2012) proposed that main idea instruction was identified as one of the highest impact instructional practices that teachers can use to improve reading comprehension [15]. Brown,S. (2018) proved that after the treatment components-explicit main idea and summarization instruction-previously identified as effective for students with reading difficulties and found effective in improving the reading comprehension for students[16].

Overall results show that the respondents have significant differences before and after using Reading Road Map in terms of inferencing and identifying the main idea. However, the result also shows that there is no significant difference before and after using the Reading Road Map in terms sequencing of events and noting significant details. This may be due to the modular distance learning modality where the respondents came from the previous years, wherein pupils are just learning by themselves. Some of them are guided by their parents, guardians, or tutors at home during the pandemic. The results may also be affected by the fact that the respondents have limited information regarding the topics. Unfamiliarity of the respondents to the words in the passage also affects their performances. Respondents experiences during the implementation are identical to the study of Plocher(2016) which reveal that more of the pupils enjoyed using Reading Road Map as reading comprehension strategy than the other strategies he used[17]. However, Reading Road Map may serve as an enrichment and supplementary material in enhancing reading comprehension skills.

CONCLUSION

1. The reading performance of the respondents in the pretest before using Reading Road Map were average in terms of sequencing of events which revealed that among the four skills, it is the easiest to do. It is followed by inferencing and noting significant details at good level. Identifying the main idea falls under the fair level which revealed that this skill is the most difficult for the respondents.
2. Considering the small improvement, the reading performance of the respondents in the post test after using Reading Road Map still falls under the average level in terms of sequencing of events. Both inferencing and noting significant details was still at a good level. However, identifying the main idea improves and falls under the good level.
3. The pre-test and post-test were significantly different in terms of inferencing and identifying the main idea. These skills were greatly affected using Reading Road Map. It helped the respondents to comprehend what they have read.

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4. Regardless of the little improvement, the pre-test and post-test of the skills such as sequencing of events and noting significant details were not significantly different. Due to respondent's unfamiliarity with the topics and words used in the passages, they could not understand the meaning of the terms which led to difficulty of understanding.

5. Meanwhile, Reading Road Map can be used as an enrichment strategy and activity that enhances the reading comprehension skills of the learners with the help of the teachers and whoever guides them in learning. In addition to this, the learners found it fun learning these skills using the Reading Road Map.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The Reading Road Map can be used by the teachers in enhancing reading comprehension skills such as sequencing of events, inferencing, noting significant details and identifying the main idea among the learners. Despite the little improvement among the four skills, there is still a development which proved that this can be an effective strategy that helps learners in comprehending what they read. The learners found it fun learning comprehension skills through Reading Road Map that lead to their active participation during the activity.

2. The passages should consist of more attractive drawings that can catch their most interest and encourage the students to enhance their reading comprehension skills. Also, provide a longer time to expose the students to the lessons about the four skills using the Reading Road Map.

3. Future researchers may conduct a similar study and contribute to a more complex study that may produce different and effective results. Future researchers should conduct unlocking of difficulties in their lesson before using Reading Road Map for a better understanding of the respondents on the terms used in every passage they read.

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